

**OA Book Usage Data Trust
Rulebook Development Overview**

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Acknowledgement

This work was made possible by the Mellon Foundation through the [Advancing to Launch by Developing IDS Governance Building Blocks](#) Grant, and by the 136 participants who contributed to online activities facilitated via the dedicated Rulebook Task Team meetings and community consultations (focus groups as well as web forms). We recognize that some of the same participants took part in multiple events. The number represents the total across all activities. Christina Drummond and Ursula Rabar designed and facilitated the processes that generated the input for this document.

Executive Summary

This document provides an overview of the process from January 2023 to March 2024 related to the development of the [OA Book Usage Data Exchange and Stewardship Rulebook version 0.0](#) including the conference based engagement, in-person facilitated workshop, Rulebook Task Team work, and community consultations via focus groups as well as web forms or surveys. The process was facilitated by the Open Access Book Usage Data Trust's (OAEBUDT) Executive Director, Christina Drummond, and Community Manager, Ursula Rabar.

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(Front cover art sourced from Canva, art provider username AndreyPopov)

Background

Community engagement has been a part of the Data Trust effort since its formation through a research partnership involving senior representatives of the Book Industry Study Group (BISG), the Curtin Open Knowledge Initiative at Curtin University (COKI), the Educopia Institute, University of Michigan Publishing, and the University of North Texas Libraries. Past community consultations explored eBook metadata¹ and usage data analytics and reporting use-cases², establishing effective methods to align development with community expectations.

In 2022 the *Advancing to Launch by Developing IDS Governance Building Blocks* award (Advancing to Launch) from the Mellon Foundation allowed a team to engage OA book stakeholders in the development of community governance mechanisms and documentation to foster trust across future data space users. Informed by the Design Principles for International Data Spaces³, participation in the International Data Spaces Association (IDSA) and a summary of legal and contractual considerations prepared by Angad Chopra and Reena Bajowala, the team recognized that a governing IDS Board of Trustees and Coordinating Office would have to be complemented by transparent community norms documented as international data space (IDS) participation “rules”, roles, and requirements.

This report summarizes the steps taken to engage community stakeholders in the identification, exploration, and development of such norms for usage data space participation. This document makes clear the process that resulted in version zero of the *Participant Rulebook for the OA Book Usage Data Trust IDS*⁴ to support trusted usage data exchange across diverse, global public and commercial OA book stakeholders.⁵

Image 1.
Rulebook Development Steps

¹ Neylon, C. (2021). OA eBook Usage (OAeBU) Metadata Community Consultation. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6422062>

² Drummond, C., & Hawkins, K. (2022). OA eBook Usage Data Analytics and Reporting Use-cases by Stakeholder. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8325578>

³ Nagel L., Lycklama D. (2021): Design Principles for Data Spaces. Position Paper. Version 1.0. Berlin <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5105744>

⁴ Drummond, C., Watson, J., Mounier, P., Elwell, J., Stern, N., Lenahan, J., Legre, Y., & Tsiavos, P. (2024). Participant Rulebook for the OA Book Usage Data Trust - International Data Space (OAEBUDT-IDS) (Version 0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11163158>

⁵ Version zero was intentionally used as sections of the first published version await content pending technical development and pilots.

Strategy

The Rulebook⁶ development strategy was designed by the Advancing to Launch project PIs Drummond (UNT), Legré (OPERAS), Manghi and Tsiavos (OpenAIRE), informed by the project advisory board (O’Leary (BISG), Watkinson (UoM), Lambert (JISC/IRUS), Elwell (EBSCO), Zucker (DeGruyter), Stern (OAPEN), Potter (TOME), Mellins-Cohen (COUNTER), Berghahn (Berghahn Books)), and the OAEBUDT’s Board of Trustees⁷. Care was taken to develop a community engagement strategy that leveraged a legal analysis of rulebook contents and existing data space rulebooks published by the International Data Spaces Association⁸ (IDSA). Professional facilitator Barbara Grant of CruxNW worked with the team to identify topics for an in-person 1.5-day workshop. A dedicated Rulebook Task Team of subject matter experts, facilitated by Christina Drummond and Ursula Rabar, further developed Rulebook details informed by public consultation and focus groups.

In this report, the development process for the first Rulebook version is documented for posterity and to potentially aid other emerging data space efforts. Sections describe the methods and tools used, as well as outputs created.

Methodology

To gather diverse feedback and points of view, the Data Trust intentionally engaged different types of OA book usage stakeholders: publishers, university presses, libraries, infrastructure and service providers, platforms, repositories, and standards bodies. Participants were based in Europe, Northern America, Africa, and Oceania. To support inclusive participation across languages, regions, and interaction styles, a mixed methods approach was applied to allow people to discuss, ideate, and contribute verbally in-person and anonymously from their own devices, both during live sessions and asynchronously. The team also intentionally sequenced stakeholder inquiries so they could peel back layers of the complex “onion” of IDS issues one at a time.

In total, from January 2023 until March 2024, the research team used six different approaches to inform Rulebook development through stakeholder feedback:

1. Live-polling during conference sessions (January - June 2023, 73 participants)
2. Pre-event surveys of “Rulebook workshop” participants (February - March 2023, 14 participants)
3. Facilitated small group discussion and activities at a 1.5 day in-person Rulebook workshop for invited experts (April 2023, 20 participants)
4. Facilitated virtual small group discussion and polling for a “Rulebook Task Team” of experts (June 2023 - March 2024, 6 participants)
5. Web-form based public consultation (August 2023 - March 2024, 7 participants)
6. Online focus groups (November 2023, 14 participants)

The rest of this section describes each of these methods in detail.

⁶Drummond, C., Watson, J., Mounier, P., Elwell, J., Stern, N., Lenahan, J., Legre, Y., & Tsiavos, P. (2024). Participant Rulebook for the OA Book Usage Data Trust - International Data Space (OAEBUDT-IDS) (Version 0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11163158>

⁷List of Trustees available at: <https://www.oabookusage.org/governance>

⁸https://docs.internationaldataspaces.org/ids-knowledgebase/v/idsa-rulebook/idsa-rulebook/1_introduction

Conference-based Engagement (January - June 2023, 73 participants)

Goal: Understand community perceptions and norms for trusted usage data exchange

Methods: To better understand what core scholarly communications users of a data space required for trusted multi-party usage data exchange, Christina Drummond and Ursula Rabar incorporated live polling into panel presentations at conferences. The themes explored included the benefits of better access to usage data, how organizations work with usage data, and thoughts about participating in a usage data-focused International Data Space as a provider or recipient of usage data feeds. Participants also remarked on issues of usage data quality and requirements for trusted usage data exchange. PowerPoint presentations were complimented by Mentimeter polls with open-text responses and voting on provided options.

Participants: Across four events, 73 individuals participated in live polling. Given the nature of these conferences, it is believed they represented library, scholarly publisher, platform and repository perspectives. The geographical location information was collected at two of the events showing a distribution across the US, Europe, Canada, Australasia and Africa.

Conference sessions were held at the annual meetings of:

- the Library Publishing Coalition (i.e the Library Publishing Forum), 23 poll participants,
- the Society of Scholarly Publishers (SSP), 18 poll participants,
- Open Repositories (Open Repositories 2023), 2 poll participants,

A presentation was also given at the *International Conference on Performance Management in Libraries* (LibPMC), 30 poll participants.

Image 2. Geographical Representation of Poll Participants at LibPMC and LPCForum

Outputs: Feedback received across the four events was published to Zenodo.⁹

⁹ Rabar, U. (2023). OAEBUDT Community Consultation Results January 2023 - July 2023. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8325572>

Rulebook Workshop Participant Pre-Event Surveys (February-March 2023, 14 participants)

Goal: Explore perceptions, requirements, and relative priorities related to usage data consistency, processing, transparency, security and risk management

Methods: To support the facilitation of in-person discussion, invited participants to the 21-22 April 2023 workshop were asked to complete two pre-event surveys in Qualtrics. Survey questions were developed by Christina Drummond, with guidance from Ursula Rabar and professional facilitator Barbara Grant. Both surveys began with multiple choice demographic questions (stakeholder type, region).

In the first survey, after demographic questions, respondents were presented with 17 questions, grouped in the following categories: Data Consistency, Data Processing & Access Transparency, Data Security, and Risk Reduction/Legal. Each of the 17 multiple-choice questions asked respondents to identify whether a given feature, functionality or policy suggested by community consultations to date or seen in other IDS models, was a “must-have”, “nice-to-have”, or “unnecessary” for an IDS focused on OA book usage data exchange. Respondents had an open text question to note any “other” items that would be required for their organization to participate in a “usage data trust”.

In the second survey, participants were asked to select all that apply from three options to reflect how they interact with usage data (generate, provide internally, or provide externally). Respondents then were asked to rate the usefulness of six potential types of usage data exchange on a scale of 1 to 5, 5 being very useful. Survey logic was applied to ask those who indicated they provide usage data to others (internal or external) to rate the importance of 13 features as “must-have”, “nice-to-have” or “unnecessary” with respect to providing confidence in the usage data they receive from other platforms through a data-exchange.” Data creators were presented with a separate list of 13 features to mark as “must-have”, “nice-to-have” or “unnecessary” with respect to importance for sharing raw usage data statistics with a third party for processing and routing.”

Survey data was aggregated to reflect the prioritization breakdowns for each feature and by stakeholder type. Anonymous open text responses were included alongside aggregate results in a report. This report was shared with participants and discussed during the workshop.

Participants: Confirmed attendees of the in-person workshop were invited to take the surveys. These included thought leaders from publishers (commercial and not-for-profit), libraries, public or not-for-profit platforms or services, and standard bodies from Europe, the US, Australasia and Africa.

Outputs: Results of both surveys were aggregated and published together in Zenodo alongside the survey questions.¹⁰

¹⁰ Drummond, C. (2023). Pre-Workshop Survey Report | 21-22 April 2023 OA Book Usage Data Exchange and Use Guidelines and Principles Meeting [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8319900>

In-person Facilitated Rulebook Workshop (April 2023, 22 participants)

Goal: Identify initial policies and participation requirements for the OAEBUDT IDS

Twenty-two invited thought leaders attended a facilitated in-person workshop hosted in the OPERAS Headquarters in Brussels. Their objective was to identify initial topics and principles for inclusion in the OAEBUDT IDS participant Rulebook document. The agenda, developed by professional facilitator Barbara Grant in collaboration with Christina Drummond and Ursula Rabar, involved minimal framing presentations followed by small group discussion and activities.

Image 3. Workshop Participants' Locations and Stakeholder Types

Methods: Presentations provided overviews of prior work including pre-workshop survey results and current community-governance. Facilitated small group discussions addressed: participant expectations, definitions, ideation and consensus around potential IDS value propositions and challenges, and the role of the IDS in managing data access and reuse. Small group ideation was supported by Mentimeter polling and facilitator recording on flip charts.

After extensive discussion, the facilitator proposed an initial set of five policy statements that the group discussed and revised using a proprietary group evaluation tool. Dr. Grant led group editing and evaluation of all statements. Twelve additional policy statements resulting from day one conversations were proposed to the group for further definition, discussion, and iteration on day two of the workshop.

Small group stations allowed participants to provide feedback on potential policy statements. Each station addressed statements related to one of the following categories:

- Who can contribute to the OAEBUDT-IDS (i.e. act as a data provider/contributor)
- OAEBUDT-IDS role in Data Stewardship
- Data Ingest Requirements
- Data Use/Reuse
- Data Management

16 statements emerged with consensus, advancing for further consultation and development. Copious notes were captured in the proceedings to inform future policy development discussions around complex issues.

Participants: This event was led by a professional facilitator Barbara Grant of Crux Consulting Consortium, with co-facilitation support provided by Christina Drummond and Ursula Rabar. Workshop participants represented 20 publishers, libraries, platforms and service providers. These contributors (in alphabetical

order) were: Vivian Berghahn (Berghahn Books), Tasha Mellins-Cohen (COUNTER Metrics), Jon Elwell (EBSCO), Björn Johansson (Springer Nature), Andrew Joseph (Wits University Press), Jennifer Kemp (then at Crossref), Sharla Lair (Lyrasis), Jo Lambert (Jisc), John Lenahan (JSTOR/ITHAKA), Pierre Mounier (OpenEdition), Cameron Neylon (Curtin University), Brian O’Leary (BISG), Yannick Legré (OPERAS), Dimitris Pierrakos (OpenAIRE), Peter Potter (TOME Project then De Gruyter), Johan Rooryck (COAlition S), Niels Stern (OAPEN), Prodromos Tsiavos (OpenAIRE), James Watson (Taylor & Francis), and Sofie Wennström (Stockholm University Press).

Outputs: The participant packet¹¹, pre-workshop survey results¹² and workshop proceedings¹³ were published in Zenodo along with the discussion paper¹⁴ provided to participants that summarized the OAEBUDT effort’s aims and IDS framework.

Rulebook Task Team (June 2023 - March 2024, 6 participants)

Goal: Develop language and policy statements for the OAEBUDT-IDS Participant Rulebook

Methods: After the April 2023 workshop, a working group referred to as the “Rulebook Task Team” was formed representing stakeholders from the publishing, library, service provider and infrastructure communities. Individuals were invited to join the working group based on involvement in the Brussels workshop and prior usage data exchange research¹⁵. Task Team participants met for 12 ninety-minute work sessions that occurred virtually between June 2023 and January 2024. Task team members also reviewed and commented using collaborative documents in between meetings. The Mellon Foundation award provided support in the amount of \$1,000 USD/person in recognition of the significant time commitment associated with this Task Team engagement.

As policy intent emerged in task team meeting discussions, staff drafted and presented back suggested rulebook language. Drafted statements were shared between meetings in online forms alongside the agreement scale provided by Dr. Grant. Language that achieved asynchronous consensus were incorporated directly into a collaborative draft rulebook document. Statements that required additional discussion were included on the next rulebook meeting agenda. Task team members also had edit access to review and comment on text as it was incorporated by Rabar and Drummond into the draft OAEBUDT-IDS rulebook document.

Drummond organized Task Team agendas, prioritizing data sharing and use and data trust participation policy statement development over technical and membership related sections that would be informed in future work packages.

¹¹ Drummond, C., Rabar, U., & Grant, B. (2023). 21-22 April 2023 OA Book Usage Data Exchange and Use Guidelines and Principles Meeting Participant Packet. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8319887>

¹² Drummond, C. (2023). Pre-Workshop Survey Report | 21-22 April 2023 OA Book Usage Data Exchange and Use Guidelines and Principles Meeting [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8319900>

¹³ Drummond, C. (2023). 21-22 April 2023 OA Book Usage Data Exchange and Use Guidelines and Principles Workshop Proceedings. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8319929>

¹⁴ Drummond, C. (2023). Rulebook Workshop Discussion Paper | Building an International Data Space for OA Book Usage. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8345034>

¹⁵ See <https://www.oabookusage.org/2020-to-2022>

Task team meetings covered the following topics related to the OAEBUDT IDS:

- Participation requirements to ensure data provider and data recipient accountability
- Transparent data disclosure requirements for usage data connectors in the OAEBUDT data space (i.e. required metadata about the usage data related to “quality” variables)
- Data sensitivity levels for various types of usage (views/downloads) and behavioral engagement data (linking, citing, reading behavior, etc.)
- Data access terms and accountability measures to ensure trust and reduce risk of harms to readers and participating OA book stakeholders
- Risk mitigation and legal liability
- Data credibility
- Draft rulebook text review and discussion

As consensus was reached on statements, the language was piped into the web-form based public consultation process described in the next section.

Image 4. Rulebook Task Team and Community Consultation Layers

Participants: Six individuals based in Europe and the US joined the working group facilitated by Drummond and Rabar: Jon Elwell (EBSCO), John Lenahan (ITHAKA/JSTOR), Niels Stern (OAPEN/DOAB), James Watson (Taylor & Francis), Pierre Mounier (OpenEdition), and Jo Lambert (JISC/IRUS). Lambert recused herself after one session due to time conflicts.

Outputs: Statements from the rulebook workshop were incorporated into a crosswalk¹⁶ alongside topics found in other data space rulebooks to provide a framework for task team discussions. After public feedback was incorporated (below), Version 0.0 of the Rulebook was published to Zenodo¹⁷.

¹⁶ Drummond, C. (2023). OA Book Usage Data Trust Rulebook Crosswalk. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8322361>

¹⁷ <https://zenodo.org/records/11163158>

Web-form Based Public Consultation (August 2023 - March 2024, 7 participants)

Goal: Asynchronous global stakeholder feedback on language emerging from the Rulebook Task Team

Global stakeholders were invited to provide feedback on drafted language for book usage data stewardship practices and policies. Issues of data quality and sensitivity, privacy, transparency, community governance, security, and data reuse were explored with respect to the book publishing ecosystem.

Methods: As language emerged from Rulebook Task Team efforts, staff presented it to community stakeholders for consultation via web form. Four separate web forms were created to support separate consultations between August 2023 and March 2024. Each introduced the respective topic, a feedback submission deadline and explained how feedback would support the rulebook development. Open, multiple choice and linear scale-type of questions were included.

The opportunity to comment was advertised via the project's social media (e.g. the 400+ followers on the @oaebu_project channel on X (formerly known as Twitter), rebroadcast to partner networks (such as the 3,000+ followers on the OPERAS channel) and posted to the public [OAEBUDT announcement list](#) (100+ subscribers).

Participants: All form submissions were anonymous as they did not collect respondents' email or IP addresses. Only the Feb-Mar 2024 form requested the geographical location information, therefore it is not possible to describe the global locations of all respondents. Despite robust advertising through partner networks, the number of participants submitting comments was extremely low. However, the comments submitted were robust, detailed, and informative.

Table 1: Consultation info by topic

Topic	Comment Period	# of Submissions Received	Consultation Advertising via X (Twitter) @OAEBU_Project
Data Provider Requirements	30 Aug - 15 Sept 2023	1	Aug 29, 2023 (975 views, 8 reposts incl. OPERAS-GER and SPARC Europe) Aug 30, 2023 (211 views, 3 reposts)
Data Quality	21 Sept - 15 Oct 2023	2	Sept 13, 2023 (308 views) Sept 21, 2023 (663 views, 5 reposts incl. DOAB, OAPEN, OA Books Network)
Data Sensitivity	31 Oct - 15 Nov 2023	0	Oct 2, 2023 (827 views, 7 reposts incl. DARIAH-EU, OAPEN, various individuals) Oct 31, 2023 (707 views, 5 reposts incl. OAPEN, DOAB, OPERAS)
Rulebook Draft	15 Feb - 7 March 2024	4	Feb 15, 2024 (369 views, 2 reposts)

Outputs: A report aggregating all forms and comments received was published in Zenodo.¹⁸

¹⁸ Rabar, U., & Drummond, C. (2024). OAEBUDT Rulebook Community Consultation Results August 2023 - March 2024. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12811238>

Online Focus Groups (November 2023, 14 participants)

Goal: Facilitate global stakeholder feedback on language emerging from the Rulebook Task Team

To address low numbers of feedback submitted via the asynchronous process and facilitate global participation from diverse stakeholders who may rely on translation tools, live focus group sessions were advertised and held via Zoom.

Methods: To accommodate different time zones, two focus groups were scheduled on November 15, 2023 (7.30 AM and 2.00 PM UTC). Sessions required registration and were advertised via the [OAEBUDT announcement list](#), social media channels, at conferences (in-person and online: Charleston Library Conference, OASPA, PUBMET) as well as by inclusion in third-party newsletters (OPERAS, LIBER, OAPEN, COUNTER, Clarke & Esposito, OASPA, NISO, ARL). Additionally, individual focus groups and web forms were advertised where applicable before the respective events/web forms went live. PowerPoint presentations relayed information alongside anonymous Mentimeter live polling. The participants were shown drafted principles prepared by the Rulebook Task Team and asked prepared questions related to:

- missing topics,
- language that caused concern,
- language that would prevent IDS participation by organizations that provide usage data (Data Providers),
- language that would prevent IDS participation by organizations that seek access to usage data (Data Recipients),
- usage metadata disclosure requirements to improve data quality transparency related to data provenance, standards compliance, reliability, frequency, granularity, and consistency, and
- balancing open principles and control over reuse given data sensitivity for the different types of usage data elements.

Participants: Across both sessions, 14 individuals participated representing libraries, university presses, publishers and service/platform providers from Europe, Canada, the US, and Africa.

*Image 5.
Focus Groups
Participants'
Locations and
Stakeholder
Types*

Results: A report of feedback received was published to Zenodo.¹⁹

¹⁹ Rabar, U., & Drummond, C. (2024). OAEBUDT Rulebook Community Consultation Results August 2023 - March 2024. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12811238>

Conclusion

Building a shared, community-developed set of data space governance principles requires substantive and substantial engagement from the diverse range of potential data space participants. For the OAEBUDT, the governance principles reflected in its Participant Rulebook took 13 months and substantial stakeholder time to develop. Engagement in the rulebook development process spanned four live polls, six virtual surveys, and 18 hours of working group discussions after 1.5 days of discussions in a dedicated workshop. As a whole, this stakeholder feedback directly supported hours of iterative rulebook drafting, ultimately resulting in the OAEBUDT's initial rulebook to guide data space participation and standard contractual clause drafting.